

Balancing quality and yield of biofuel and biochar in the pyrolysis of industrial macroalgae sludge: future perspectives with a circular economy approach in the EU FLEXBY project

E. Ciurcina, R. Pardo, L. Taboada-Ruiz, J. Holgado, P. Álvarez Rodríguez, M. Díaz-Somoano, B. Ruiz
Carbon Science and Technology Institute (INCAR), CSIC. C/ Francisco Pintado Fe 26, 33011, Oviedo, Spain.

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Presenting author email: begorb@incar.csic.es

Introduction

The accumulation of algal bio-waste, particularly in the form of solid waste from industrial processing of macroalgae, poses significant environmental and human health challenges. The presence of large quantities of untreated algal waste can lead to ecosystem imbalances such as oxygen depletion in aquatic environments, harmful algal blooms and the release of greenhouse gases during decomposition. In addition, inappropriate disposal of bio-waste contributes to soil and water pollution, which can affect marine biodiversity and local fisheries. From a public health perspective, decomposing algae can release toxic compounds and unpleasant odours, posing a risk to air quality and public well-being. Given the increasing global production of macroalgae for food, pharmaceuticals and bio-based materials, it is imperative to implement sustainable strategies to manage and reuse these wastes (Pardilhó et al., 2021). The valorisation of algal bio-waste into valuable bio-based products and energy sources offers a promising solution to mitigate its negative environmental impact, while supporting the transition towards a circular bio-economy, and has shown a high potential for bio-energy production (Anacleto et al., 2025).

The purpose of this work was to examine the feasibility of using industrial macroalgae sludge as a potentially valuable resource. This analysis was carried out with the aim of obtaining, through thermal pyrolysis processes, bioenergy and bioproducts, thus avoiding the need for landfill or incineration. In accordance with the guidelines of the EU FLEXBY Project, the experimental variables of conventional pyrolysis will be optimised to maximise the bio-oil and gas yield.

Methodology

The sludge sample was obtained from the wastewater treatment plant of a company located in northern Spain and recognised as the largest agar-agar producer in Europe. The industrial procedure for the extraction of agar-agar from the red macroalga *Gelidium corneum* has been documented in the publication of Ferrera-Lorenzo et al. (2014). Given the industrial origin of this waste, the sludge sample was meticulously collected, dried and prepared to a particle size suitable for characterization and pyrolysis.

The sludge industrial sample was characterised in order to ascertain its physico-chemical properties and its suitability for pyrolysis processes. The characterisation included proximate and ultimate analysis, inorganic composition, calorific value, thermogravimetric analysis, and other relevant analyses. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted to ascertain the thermal behaviour of the sludge industrial sample.

Conventional pyrolysis was carried out in a specially designed horizontal cylindrical electric furnace. The sample was introduced into the furnace at room temperature, and a flow of 100 ml/min of nitrogen gas was passed through to create an inert atmosphere inside the reactor. The heating protocol of the furnace was set at a rate of 25°C/min, with final pyrolysis temperatures ranging from 450 to 750°C and residence times of 1 hour at the desired pyrolysis temperature. Following the thermal process, three distinct fractions (biochar, bio-oil and gas) were collected, quantified and analyzed.

Results

Proximate analysis of this sludge sample showed high ash content (41.07%) and substantial volatile matter content (51.25%). The ultimate analysis showed a moderate carbon content (28.58%) and an important nitrogen content (5.47%).

The inorganic composition of the biowaste (see Fig. 1) is obtained by XRF chemical analysis of the sludge ash. The sludge displays a high concentration of chemical elements, including calcium (Ca), silicon (Si),

magnesium (Mg), phosphorus (P), sodium (Na), potassium (K), and iron (Fe). The high concentration of Si in this macroalgae sludge is normal. This is due to the abundance of sand associated with the macroalgae, which is subsequently discharged to the treatment plant.

The yield of pyrolysis products is contingent upon the experimental pyrolysis conditions. As can be seen in **Table 1**, the yield of biochar, bio-oil and gas varies significantly when the macroalgae sludge is subjected to conventional pyrolysis at temperatures ranging from 450 to 750°C.

The yield of biochar is at its highest (47%) at low temperature conditions (450 °C), whilst higher temperatures are conducive to gas production.

In the context of bio-oil, the maximum yield (30%) is attained at both 500 and 750 °C, indicating that, from an energy efficiency standpoint, it is more advantageous to operate the process at the lower temperature to maximise savings.

Conclusions

The European Flexby Project aims to develop heavy biofuels for the transport sector using microwave pyrolysis processes from biomasses, including various industrial biogenic sewage sludge. In the framework of this project, a sewage sludge residue from the agar-agar industry has been used and subjected to conventional pyrolysis, which will later be compared with microwave pyrolysis. The impact of conventional pyrolysis temperature was examined as a critical variable to optimise biochar, bio-oil and gas yields. It has been observed that at low pyrolysis temperature the bio-oil yield is optimised. All processes have been demonstrated to produce a high level of biochar, with the maximum yield (47%) being achieved at the lowest temperature (450°C).

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Fig. 1. Inorganic composition of macroalgae sludge waste.

Table 1. Yield of the pyrolysis fractions obtained at different temperatures

Pyrolysis Temperature (°C)	Biochar yield (%)	Bio-oil yield (%)	Gas yield (%)
450	47	25	27
500	46	30	23
600	43	27	30
750	41	30	28